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Assessing and Mitigating Power Quality Issues in Tidal Energy Integrated Distributed Networks: A Comparative Analysis of Custom Power Devices

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Abstract

Advancements in power electronics have enhanced the integration of marine renewable energy (MRE) sources like tidal and wave power into the electrical grid, improving efficiency and reliability. However, integrating tidal energy introduces unique challenges due to its intermittent nature, which can lead to power quality (PQ) issues such as voltage fluctuations, flickers, harmonics, and frequency variations. These challenges become more pronounced with larger tidal energy systems and nonlinear loads in weak distribution networks. This study employs MATLAB/Simulink simulations to evaluate Custom Power Devices (CPD) like Unified Power Quality Conditioner (UPQC), Distributed Static Compensator (DSTATCOM), and Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR) for addressing PQ issues in grid-connected tidal energy systems. Comparing their performance, the research highlights UPQC's efficacy in stabilizing both energy source and load sides. This insight aids system planners and operators in designing reliable grid-tied tidal energy systems.

Keywords: Tidal Energy; Power Quality; Custom Power Devices; UPQC

1. Introduction

With the advancement of power electronics, the integration of marine renewable Energy (MRE) sources like tidal and wave into the electrical grid has become more efficient and reliable [1]. However, integrating tidal energy with the electrical grid poses unique challenges that require careful consideration to ensure stable operation. The inherent intermittency and variability of tidal energy source (TES) can cause different power quality (PQ) issues such as, voltage sag/swell, flickers, harmonics, power factor, and frequency variations, which can lead to unstable and unreliable grid operation [2,3]. These issues become more prominent with the increasing size and penetration of TES and the incorporation of nonlinear and dynamic loads into the electrical grid, particularly in weak distribution networks. Besides, the lack in research regarding PQ analysis of TES presents a significant challenge in successfully deploying these promising renewable energy technologies in the commercial sector. Therefore, careful planning and advanced technologies are required to mitigate these concerns and ensure the safe, economical, and reliable integration of tidal energy into the electrical grid.

Different custom power devices such as UPQC, DSTATCOM, DVR, etc., can be used to mitigate these issues and enhance the overall system performance [4]. Among these compensating devices, UPQC is emerging as an attractive solution due to its flexibility and ability to provide comprehensive PQ mitigation [5]. It can deal with both voltage and current quality concerns simultaneously, unlike the DVR and DSTATCOM, which can only address one of these

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challenges individually. It consists of both series and shunt active filters, where the shunt filter handles load current harmonics, and the series filter deals with voltage sags and swells. To assess the effectiveness of the abovementioned compensating devices in mitigating power quality challenges in tidal energy based distributed networks, simulation studies have been conducted using MATLAB/Simulink. Performance of UPQC is compared with DSTATCOM and DVR under different dynamics (Table 1). The simulation results show that UPQC can effectively mitigate quality concerns from both source and load sides in the grid-tied TES.

Table 1. Comparison of different custom power devices

Factors	DVR	DSTATCOM	UPQC
Rating	High	Low	High (higher ratings)
Operational speed	Fast	Less than DVR	Faster
Architecture	Series	Shunt	Both series & shunt
Power	Active/Reactive	Reactive	Both
Harmonics	Very less	Less	Lesser
PQ mitigation	Sag/Swell/Harmonics	Sag/Swell	Sag, Swell, Harmonics, Flicker, Transients, Unbalance
Cost	High	Nominal	Higher

Fig. 1. Power conversion architecture of PMSG based direct drive grid tied tidal energy with control.

2. System Model

The accurate modeling of the grid-tied tidal energy system is crucial for controller design and performance evaluation. This section outlines the mathematical modeling of the tidal turbine, power electronic converters, UPQC, grid interface, and associated control systems. An overview of the direct drive PMSG-based tidal turbine power conversion architecture is shown in Fig. 1. The system is composed of a direct-drive tidal turbine coupled to a PMSG. The diode-based full bridge rectifier is used to convert variable three-phase generated AC supply into variable DC supply. UPQC is connected between the source and the grid through the series (DVR) and shunt (DSTATCOM) converters for effective power transmission and power quality mitigations [6,7].

Tidal Turbine Model The total mechanical power generated by marine current turbine is described as follows [8]:

$$P_m = 0.5 \rho C_p (\beta, \lambda) A v_t^3 \quad (1)$$

Where, P_m is the generated mechanical power, v_t is the tidal speed, ρ is the tidal density, C_p is the power coefficient, β denotes the pitch angle, A is the swept area of the tidal turbine blades. λ is the tip-speed ratio which is defined as:

$$\lambda = \frac{\omega_m R}{v} \quad (2)$$

where ω_m is the rotor speed, R is the blades radius. The power coefficient C_p can be described as follows:

$$C_p(\beta, \lambda) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{116}{\lambda_i} - 0.4\beta - 5 \right) e^{\frac{-21}{\lambda_i}} \quad (3)$$

$$\lambda_i^{-1} = (\lambda + 0.08\beta)^{-1} - 0.035(1 + \beta^3)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

2.1. PMSG and Power Converter Modeling

Higher efficiency and power factor, absence of a gearbox system, no regular maintenance, flexible active and reactive power control, and dissipation are making PMSG prominent in low-speed wind/tidal-based energy generation. The PMSG is modeled based on [8]. The diode bridge rectifier and the DC-DC boost converter are modeled as per [9]. Table 2 gives the parameters of simulated system.

Table 2. Parameters of Simulated System.

Tidal Turbine Parameters	Values	UPQC Parameters	Values
Rated Power	30 kW	Series Transformer (T1)	4 kVA
Rotor Radius	4 m	Shunt Inductor (L1)	1.39 mH
Rated speed	2.5 m/s	Nonlinear load	15kW
Water density	1024 kg/m ³	Frequency	60 Hz
PMSG Parameters	Values	DC link	6.668 mF
Stator Phase Resistance	0.045 ohm	Shunt Controller	$K_p=1000, K_i=1200$
Stator Inductance (L_d, L_q)	6.03 mH	Series d-controller	$K_p=1, K_i=1$
Flux linkage	0.97 (V.s)	Series q-controller	$K_p=8, K_i=10$
Pole Pairs	40	Switching frequency	10 kHz

2.2. Control Architecture

This section gives the control architectures used to generate the PWM signal for the series and shunt converters of UPQC with boost converter of TECS as shown in Fig.1. The series compensator utilizes various compensation methods with the main goal of injecting voltage aligned with the grid phase to minimize the injected voltage. A PLL extracts fundamental PCC voltage, generating the reference load voltage. The compensator's reference voltage is determined by subtracting PCC voltage from the load reference, and actual compensator voltages stem from the difference between load and PCC voltages. PI controllers process this difference for appropriate reference signals, which are converted to abc domain for PWM voltage control, generating gating signals for the series compensator. For efficient power tracking of variable speed tidal turbine, Perturb and Observe (P&O) based MPPT control is designed. A PI controller maintains the dc-link voltage and generates the loss power current. For load current compensation, the shunt compensator uses a synchronous reference frame (SRF) technique, converting load currents to d-q-0 domain with PLL and source voltage input. The computed d axis load current is subtracted from the output of the PI control to calculate the reference d axis current and is converted to abc domain reference grid currents. The reference grid currents are compared with the sensed grid currents in a hysteresis current controller to generate the gating pulses for the shunt converter [7].

2.3. Power Quality

Power quality issues pose significant challenges for tidal energy integration, particularly due to the intermittent nature of tides and the impact of factors like voltage fluctuations, harmonics, and transient disturbances. These issues can disrupt synchronization, cause waveform distortions, and affect microgrid stability. A robust power quality management strategy is crucial to mitigate these impacts, ensuring the smooth integration of tidal energy, optimal energy use, and overall system reliability. The main causes include the intermittency of marine energy sources,

Table 3. Dynamic events simulated

PQ Issues	Duration
Voltage Sag	t= 1-1.2 sec
Voltage Swell	t= 1.4-1.6 sec
Current Harmonics	t= 0.15-0.3 sec
Interruption	t= 0.5-0.7 sec
Source Variation	t= 0-0.5 sec

transient events like islanding, non-linear loads, phase imbalances, and electromagnetic interferences. These issues are more pronounced in weak distribution networks.

3. Simulation Result

The simulation results show the impact of UPQC in mitigating different PQ issues. The simulated dynamic PQ events with the time duration are mentioned in Table 3.

3.1. Voltage fluctuations: Fig. 2 and Fig.3 depict the dynamic response of the UPQC during voltage sags ($t=1-1.2s$) and swells ($t=1.4-1.6s$). The series compensator effectively mitigates the grid voltage disturbances by injecting suitable voltages in the opposite phase, maintaining the load voltage at the rated condition.

Fig. 2. Voltage at grid and Load bus (a) without UPQC; (b) With UPQC

Fig. 3. Voltage at grid and Load bus (a) without UPQC; (b) With UPQC

3.2. Nonlinear load: Fig.4 shows the performance of UPQC under nonlinear load, Nonlinear loads introduce harmonic currents into the system, which can lead to current waveform distortion. The shunt compensator in UPQC actively filters out these harmonic currents, reducing their impact on the grid current.

Fig. 4. (a) without UPQC; (b) With UPQC

3.3. Interruption: In Fig. 5, under a load unbalance condition where phase "c" of the load is disconnected at $t = 0.5$ s, the UPQC shows sinusoidal grid current. Load voltage and grid voltage are maintained at rated values.

Fig. 5. (a) Grid/Load current during interruption with UPQC; (b) Tidal and rotor speed profile

3.4. Varying tidal speed: Another event simulated is the varying tide speed. As shown in Fig.5 (b) the tide speed is varied between 1 m/s to 2 m/s. Fig. 6 shows that the integrated system could compensate for the voltage sags at load bus due to variation in tide speed.

Fig. 6. (a) without UPQC; (b) With UPQC

4. Conclusion

It is essential to address the research gap in PQ analysis of TES integrated distributed network to facilitate the widespread adoption of this as sustainable sources of electricity. This paper reviews PQ issues that can arise in grid-tied TES and demonstrates the simulation based comparative analysis of custom power devices in mitigating these issues. The simulation results highlight the potential of UPQC as a viable solution for power quality mitigation in TES leading to more stable and reliable operation. This study provides useful insights for system operators and planners in the design and operation of grid-tied tidal energy systems. Evaluating the efficiency and cost of tidal energy systems with custom power devices and investigating the effect of grid inertia on power quality will be the primary research objectives in the future.

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